

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF ECOLOGICAL AND ETHICAL EDUCATIONAL SKILLS IN THE FORMATION OF A CHILD AS A MATURE PERSON

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Abstract. *In this article, while discussing the role and importance of ecological-ethical education skills in the formation of a child as a mature person, the content of environmental ethics education by improving ecological-ethical education is highlighted. Also, the thoughts about forming a positive attitude of the child to the environment, his conscious understanding of the place of the elements of nature in human life, and having a broad and clear vision of the landscape of the world have also been reflected.*

Keywords: *child, education, ecological education, pedagogue, ethics, elements of nature, personal qualities, ecological consciousness, educational skills, environment, nature conservation.*

We believe that the role and importance of ecological and moral education skills in the formation of a child as a mature person is important. Therefore, it is possible to explain the importance of ecological upbringing of children by clarifying the nature of these concepts (i.e., ecological outlook, ecological culture, ecological consciousness).

Ecological worldview means a conscious perception that preservation of the external environment, necessary for a person's moderate living, is an urgent issue of vital importance. In essence, the formation of a healthy ecological worldview in an individual means that the ecological culture has been established in the whole society, therefore, ecological education and training, with the formation of an ecological worldview as the main goal, should be one of the priority and vitally important tasks of the state. Ecological worldview as a developing skill includes a number of components, and each of these components has a certain influence on the formation of ecological worldview at the necessary level [3].

In order to fully ensure the continuity of the process of the development of the child's personality, there are no structures of influence on the formation of the ecological worldview by various educational institutions (environmental conversations organized with elementary school students consist of complex lectures, is not conducted in the form of live communication, therefore, the importance will not be as expected);

- some shortcomings in the implementation of educational work based on rational thinking for the emotional-symbolic perception of the environment and nature by young students [2, p. 7].

It is possible to create a foundation for the development of his ecological worldview by forming environmental awareness, ecological culture and knowledge of environmental law in a person. One of the first steps of this task is to improve environmental education within primary education.

We believe that by improving the child's environmental education, it is possible to form his environmental ethics as a person. Therefore, it is possible to explain the importance of

ecological upbringing of children by clarifying the nature of these concepts (i.e., ecological outlook, ecological culture, ecological consciousness).

Clarification of basic knowledge in the field of ecology, i.e., what level of basic knowledge a primary school student should acquire in order to have a comprehensive environmental education, in the "Concept of Development of Environmental Education in the Republic of Uzbekistan" is shown in a recommended table of contents. According to this document, in order for elementary school students to have a moderate level of environmental ethics (education), in addition to the academic subjects: "water conservation, the importance of atmospheric air and its protection, earth rational use of resources and underground resources, protection of flora and fauna, collection and disposal of waste, preservation of the beautiful and unique nature of Uzbekistan, active participation in the preservation of the nature of the village (city) where he lives. It is specified that "he should have general knowledge and skills about reserves and nature parks in Uzbekistan, about the tragedy of the Aral Sea".

The issue of ensuring harmony between elementary ecological knowledge and the picture of the world in the child's imagination is one of the issues that has attracted the attention of a number of experts. Based on the opinion of experts, we present below the system of knowledge, information and information that forms the content of environmental knowledge of a primary school student:

- to know the description and characteristics of at least 25 terms that are widely used in modern ecology and are mentioned in the description of local and regional environmental problems (for example, "Forest fund", "Fresh water reserve", "Soil degradation", "Land salinity" such concepts as "air pollution");

- being able to tell and justify 10 facts about the climate of their place of residence and the declining wildlife (for example, "This year, the lowest temperature in winter fell to -150", "What is the reason for the abnormal heat?", "Which species of birds will is decreasing?")

- to have general information about the activities of state and public organizations engaged in nature protection;

- to know basic information about the types of punishments applied by the local nature protection state bodies for environmental violations;

- to have general information about the activities of international nature protection organizations;

- to be able to generally describe rivers, mountains, lakes and similar natural objects in the area of residence;

- it is necessary to have information about the protected and protected natural objects in one's living area and to know enough about birds, plant and animal species, historical objects of republican importance [6 , pp. 36-37].

Ecological worldview means a conscious perception that preservation of the external environment, necessary for a person's moderate living, is an urgent issue of vital importance. In essence, the formation of a healthy ecological worldview in an individual means that the ecological culture has been established in the whole society, therefore, ecological education and training, with the formation of an ecological worldview as the main goal, should be one of the priority and vitally important tasks of the state. Ecological worldview as a developing skill includes a number of components, and each of these components has a certain influence on the formation of ecological worldview at the necessary level. Researchers` (Sh.Otaboyev, M.Nabiyev) ecological worldview

consists of such components as knowledge of elements of nature and natural phenomena, positive attitude towards the environment, ecological awareness, skills related to mastering ecological culture, and knowledge in the field of environmental law believes that it is desirable that the acquisition (or formation) of each of them should be carried out in harmony with national values from the initial stages of education [3].

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